

EFFECTS OF DETOMIDINE ON PHYSIOLOGICAL INDICES IN DOMESTIC PIGEONS (*Columba livia*)

M.S. ISMAILA AND K.I. ONIFADE

Department of Veterinary Physiology and Pharmacology, Faculty of Veterinary Medicine Usmanu Danfodiyo University Sokoto

ABSTRACT

The effects of detomidine on cloacal temperature, respiratory rate, and heart rates, were evaluated in domestic pigeons. Six birds were used in each of four treatment groups. Detomidine was administered at a dose range of 250µg/kg, 500 µg/kg, 750µg/kg, and 1000 µg/kg intramuscularly. In each of the mentioned doses, the above physiological parameters were determined and recorded before the drug administration and at interval of 15minutes, up to the time when the birds recovered from sedation. There was significant decrease in the physiological parameters ($p<0.05$) from the baseline values. Significant differences also existed between the four treatment groups. But the decrease in these values were transient, which makes detomidine a good immobilizing agent in pigeons.

KEYWORDS- Detomidine, physiology, pigeons, immobilization

INTRODUCTION:

Detomidine Hydrochloride (Domosedan[®]) is a sedative –analgesic, more potent than xylazine, with greater specificity at central α_2 -adrenoreceptors (Virtanen and MacDonald 1985). It has been shown that α_2 –adrenergic receptors are widely distributed in the brain of Japanese quail (Ball *et al.*, 1989), Pekin duck (Muller and Gerstberger 1992, 1997), Pigeon and Chick (Fernandez Lopez *et al.*, 1997, Revilla *et al.*, 1998). Detomidine induces cardiovascular effects similar to xylazine. Decrease myocardial contractility, bradycardia, and biphasic blood pressure response may occur after I.V injection (Wagner *et al.*, 1991). It has been reported by Muhammed *et al.*, 1993 that respiratory rate decreases significantly in chickens when 0.3mg/kg detomidine was combined with ketamine. Hypothermia was observed by Durrani *et al.*, 2005 after detomidine administration in quails. Safe and effective sedation and anesthesia are very important in birds (just as for other animals) not only for surgical procedures but also for safe handling and diagnostic procedures (Durrani *et al.*, 2005). Due to effects observed on the cardiopulmonary system and thermoregulatory mechanisms in birds and other animals using α_2 –agonist drugs, further research is necessary using these drugs. This research, monitor these parameters up to the recovery periods so as to ascertain the trends in changes that occurs after administration of these drugs in pigeons.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Twenty four healthy domesticated pigeons of both sexes were acclimatized for two weeks before commencement of the experiment. They were fed with grains and groundnut, water was given ad-libitum. Four different doses of detomidine 250µg/kg, 500 µg/kg, 750µg/kg, and 1000 µg/kg were used. Six pigeons were assigned to each of the above given doses. The drug was injected into the deep pectoral muscle using tuberculin syringe. Stethoscope and a tally counter were used to obtain the Heart and respiratory rates; while a digital thermometer was inserted into the cloacae to obtain the Cloacal temperature. These parameters were taken before the drug administration and at intervals of 15minutes after the drug administration up to recovery period. Data were expressed as means (\pm SD) of 6 birds. The means were subjected to ANOVA and Values for ($p<0.05$) were considered significant.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of the study were summarized in Tables 1-3.

TABLE 1. Mean (\pm S.D) Heart Rates (Beats/Min) Following Detomidine Administration in Pigeons (*Columba Livia*)

Time (Mins.)	Treatment Groups			
	1	2	3	4
0	224.6 \pm 21.84	234.00 \pm 11.94	226.00 \pm 19.15	228.83 \pm 22.87
15	123.67 \pm 19.27*	116.00 \pm 17.95*	135.33 \pm 17.35*	120.67 \pm 31.36*
30	106.67 \pm 28.16*	105.33 \pm 23.96*	117.33 \pm 9.71*	92.67 \pm 15.73*+
45	121.66 \pm 18.05*	104.33 \pm 31.88*+	112.33 \pm 16.02*	92.67 \pm 12.74*+
60	161.33 \pm 34.38*	126.00 \pm 28.35*+	134.67 \pm 23.51*+	100.67 \pm 14.13*+
75	185.33 \pm 28.72*	145.33 \pm 34.69*+	140.66 \pm 22.68*+	116.00 \pm 19.13*+
90	213.00 \pm 18.61	165.33 \pm 40.12*+	146.67 \pm 14.91*+	123.33 \pm 24.59*+
105	220.00 \pm 16.48	198.00 \pm 31.89	165.33 \pm 27.19*+	132.00 \pm 25.72*+
120	213.00 \pm 18.61	213.33 \pm 14.49	194.17 \pm 13.40*+	151.33 \pm 27.17*+
135	220.00 \pm 16.49	219.33 \pm 1783	203.33 \pm 13.15	164.50 \pm 26.84*+
150	221.00 \pm 15.39	214.66 \pm 6.69	218.00 \pm 15.42	211.50 \pm 8.86

*Significantly different from the baseline values (P<0.05), n=6, +Significantly different from treatment 1 (P<0.05), Treatment 1 (250 μ g/kg detomidine), Treatment 2 (500 μ g/kg detomidine), Treatment 3 (750 μ g/kg detomidine), Treatment 4 (1000 μ g/kg detomidine)

TABLE 2 Mean (\pm S.D) Respiratory Rates (Cycles/Min) Following Detomidine Administration in Pigeons (*Columba Livia*)

Time (Mins.)	Treatment Groups			
	1	2	3	4
0	58.67 \pm 5.49	54.67 \pm 4.98	54.40 \pm 6.11	62.00 \pm 6.83
15	36.00 \pm 10.52*	34.00 \pm 6.00*	34.70 \pm 3.77*	44.00 \pm 5.66*
30	32.67 \pm 5.38*	29.33 \pm 1.88*	29.30 \pm 2.198*	36.67 \pm 8.77*
45	33.33 \pm 5.96*	28.00 \pm 4.61*	28.70 \pm 2.75*	35.67 \pm 9.71*
60	40.00 \pm 6.53*	32.00 \pm 6.11*	31.0 \pm 4.27*	32.67 \pm 1.49*+
75	48.67 \pm 7.08*	36.67 \pm 5.85*	34.00 \pm 2.00*+	36.00 \pm 5.66*+
90	51.33 \pm 2.75*	41.33 \pm 8.53*	25.60 \pm 1.89*+	46.67 \pm 4.85*+
105	56.00 \pm 4.00	45.33 \pm 8.21*	42.00 \pm 2.00*+	42.67 \pm 3.77*+
120	57.00 \pm 1.52	50.67 \pm 9.14	44.70 \pm 2.75*+	46.00 \pm 3.06*+
135	53.00 \pm 5.13	49.67 \pm 2.75	50.60 \pm 8.22	57.33 \pm 2.75
150	60.00 \pm 4.00	56.00 \pm 4.00	54.70 \pm 6.80	60.33 \pm 4.60

n = 6, *Significantly different from the baseline values (P<0.05), +Significantly different from treatment 1 (P<0.05), Treatment 1 (250 μ g/kg detomidine), Treatment 2 (500 μ g/kg detomidine), Treatment 3 (750 μ g/kg detomidine), Treatment 4 (1000 μ g/kg detomidine)

TABLE 3 Mean (\pm S.D) Cloacal Temperature ($^{\circ}$ C) Following Detomidine Administration in Pigeons (*Columba livia*)

Time (Mins.)	Treatment Groups			
	1	2	3	4
0	41.88 \pm 0.17	41.85 \pm 0.21	41.90 \pm 0.18	41.05 \pm 0.25
15	40.62 \pm 0.93	40.56 \pm 0.92	40.00 \pm 0.53	40.40 \pm 0.60
30	39.83 \pm 1.37	39.67 \pm 1.28*	39.10 \pm 0.87*	39.25 \pm 0.88*
45	40.35 \pm 1.12	39.87 \pm 1.31*	38.70 \pm 1.04* ⁺	38.30 \pm 0.41* ⁺
60	40.85 \pm 0.97	40.32 \pm 1.19	38.40 \pm 0.77* ⁺	38.78 \pm 0.79* ⁺
75	41.62 \pm 0.53	40.65 \pm 1.21	38.60 \pm 1.03* ⁺	39.25 \pm 0.99* ⁺
90	41.95 \pm 0.07	40.85 \pm 1.23	39.20 \pm 1.04* ⁺	39.84 \pm 0.62* ⁺
105	41.93 \pm 0.07	41.131.06	40.10 \pm 1.33	40.35 \pm 0.60
120	41.97 \pm 0.04	41.62 \pm 0.44	40.80 \pm 0.83	40.83 \pm 0.39
135	41.97 \pm 0.04	41.60 \pm 6.64	41.40 \pm 0.70	41.28 \pm 0.20
150	42.0 \pm 0.30	41.62 \pm 6.44	41.60 \pm 6.64	41.45 \pm 6.24

n =6, *Significantly different from the baseline values (P<0.05), ⁺Significantly different from treatment 1 (P<0.05), Treatment 1 (250 μ g/kg detomidine), Treatment 2 (500 μ g/kg detomidine), Treatment 3 (750 μ g/kg detomidine), Treatment 4 (1000 μ g/kg detomidine)

From the results it shows clearly that detomidine has a dose-dependent effect on physiological parameters; the decrease in heart and respiratory rates was dose-dependent with the higher doses producing a significant decrease in both parameters at comparable periods after administration. This was in agreement with previous studies in other domestic and wild animals using the drug. In goats (Jang *et al* 1989; Singh *et al* 1991; Clark *et al* 1993; Sleeman 1997; Dilipkumar *et al* 1998; and Onifade 2007). similar results on the effects of this drug were obtained using different routes of administration. In other species similar results were obtained on the heart and respiratory rates after detomidine administration (Vainio 1985; Reitmeyer *et al* 1986; Singh *et al* 1991; Daunt *et al* 1993; Lavoie *et al* 1996). In chickens Muhammed *et al.*, 1993 observed a significant decrease in respiratory rate after detomidine administration. The decrease in rectal temperature observed using the higher doses in this study also coincide with what Durrani *et al* 1995 reported in quails .It is recommended therefore whenever detomidine and other α_2 -agonist are to be used for immobilization in pigeons and other birds, a complete data set of physiological parameters should be obtain before, and at 15mins intervals during any surgical or clinical procedure because of their potential effects on physiological indices.

REFERENCES

- Ball G.F. Nock B. McEwew B.S. Balthazart J (1989) Distribution of α_2 -adrenergic receptors in the brain of Japanese Quail as determined by quantitative autography: implications for the control of sexually dimorphic reproductive process. *Brain Res* 491: Pp 68-79.
- Clarke T.P. Purohit R.C and Wilson R.C (1993) Evaluation of sedative and analgesic properties of detomidine in goats. *Agri.Pract* 14(4)29-33.
- Daunt A. Dunlop C.I. Shater S.L. Ruskoah Sci. B.S. Vakkuri O. Hudgson D.S. Tyler L.M. and Maze A.P. Chapman P.L 1993. Cardiopulmonary and behavioral responses to computer-driven infusion of detomidine in standing horses. *Am .J. Vet. Res.* 54(12) 2075-2083.
- Dilipkumar D. Sharma A.K and Gupta O.P. 1998. Comparative cardiopulmonary effects of xylazine and detomidine in goats. *Indian Vet. J* 75(10) 899-900.
- Durrani U.F. Ashraf M and Khalid A. (2005) Comparative Efficacy of Detomidine and Detomidine-Ketamine cocktail in quails. *Parkistan Vet. J* 25(4):2005

Fernandez-Lopez A. Revilla V. Candelas Gonzalez- gil J. Diaz A. Pazos A. (1988) Study of alpha-2 and beta-adrenoceptor distribution in pigeons and chick brain. *Eur .J. Neurosci.*9: Pp 972-883.

Mohammed F. K. Al-Badrany M.S. Al-Hassan A.M (1993) Detomidine-Ketamine anesthesia in chickens. *Vet.Rec* 133-192.

Jang K.H. Nam T.C and Kweon O.K (1989) Effects of Detomidine hydrochloride on bloodpressure and acid-base balance in goats. *J. Korean Soc. Vet. Clin. Med.*6(1) 35-44.

Lavoie J.P. Phan S.T. and Blais D(1996). Effectiveness of a combination of Detomidine and Butaphanol on respiratory function in horses with or without chronic obstructive pulmonary disease. *Am. J. Vet. Res.* 57(5): 705-709.

Muller A.R. Gerstberger R (1992). The alpha-2-adrenergic receptor system in the hypothalamus of the pekin duck. *Cell, tissue. Res.* 268 Pp 98-107.

Onifade K.I. (2007) Pharmacological effects of Detomidine, Medetomidine and Atipamizole in Sokoto red goats. A PhD thesis in the Department Veterinary Physiology and Pharmacology, Faculty of veterinary Medicine, University of Ibadan. Ibadan, Nigeria.

Reitemeyer H, Klein H.J. and Deegen E(1986)The effects of sedatives on lung function in horses. *Acta.Vet.Scand.*82:111-120.

Sleeman J.M. Carter.W. Tobin T. and Ramsay E.C (1997) Immobilization of domestic goats (*Capra hircus*) using orally administered carfentanil citrate and detomidine hydrochloride. *J. Zoo Wildlife Med.* 28(2). 158-165.

Virtanen, R., and MacDonalds E(1985) Comparison of effect of Detomidine and xylazine on alpha-2-adrenoceptor-mediated responses in the central and peripheral nervous system. *Eur J. Pharmacol* 115(2):277-284.

Singh, A.P Singh J. Peshin P.K. Sharif D. and Patil D.B (1991) Evaluation of Detomidine as a sedative in buffaloes. *Indian. J. Anim.Sci.*61, 1074-1078.

Wagner, A.E. Muir.W.W. and Hinchcliff K.W (1991) Cardiovascular effects of xylazine and Detomidine in horses. *Am. J. Vet. Res* 52(5): 651-57.

Received for Publication: 21/05/2009

Accepted for Publication: 20/07/2009

Corresponding Author:

Ismaila M.S,

Department of Veterinary Physiology and Pharmacology, Faculty of Veterinary Medicine Usmanu Danfodiyo University Sokoto

E-mail address- eemani2002@yahoo.com